

NOVEL APPROACH TO AQUATIC BODIES LOCOMOTION: PART 3: PECTORAL FIN SOURCE OF POWER

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ABSTRACT

The area of fish locomotion is infested with the prevailing and dominating model which violates the first and second laws of thermodynamics. The prevailing model avers that von Karman's vortices are responsible for fish aquatic bodies propulsion. For the first time, this model was scrutinized and the conceptional errors were exposed in the first paper of this series. In the second paper in this series, the long construction process of building models started which describes the various effects of the tail (caudal fin) and other fins. The current paper inserts science into the modeling of a specific category of pectoral fins. The fourth paper deals with the undulating fins and the reverse "tail" propulsion (like the Trigger fish).

Here, the focus is on the pectoral fin. The understanding how fin works and the significance of the various parameters is examined. It seems that if the fin moves in the same speed back and forth, the net thrust is zero since the fin cannot bend during return of the fin. The most intuitive idea to explain the locomotion is the change of the cross area. This idea might be more correct for diving birds like puffins which are not exactly aquatic creatures. For most aquatic creatures like fish, who spend almost all of the time in the water, this statement is not correct. It turned out that the rotating and undulation of the fin do help to improve or create propulsion but not significantly. Yet, the main contributors are different mechanisms. The main mechanisms for most fishes that control the pectoral fin propulsion are the different angular velocity at distinct phases, and the operation angles in the yaw direction range. This explanation becomes obvious after checking the model, but remember that for the last over 100 years of research in this area, no one proposed or considered it.

NOMENCLATURE

A_b	Area ratio
F	Force
F_d	Ratio of fin depth to fish length
F_l	Ratio of fin length to fish length
h	Height of pectoral fin
g	Gravity constant
L	Pectoral fin height
m	The (fish) mass
n	Coefficient for the tail's height
r	Local distance from the armpit
R	Maximum distance from the armpit
t	Time
t^*	Time to cross jet area
U	fish velocity
x	Distance in straight (movement) direction
y	Distance perpendicular to x

Greek Letters

γ	Angle from the body
ω	Angular velocity
ρ	density
θ	angle
ξ	Dimensionless distance

Key Words

Pectoral Fin, Fish, Propulsion, Second law, Locomotion, Thermodynamics of Locomotion, Aquatic, Creature, analytical models, BCF

1 Introduction

For more than 50 years, the “model” for aquatic bodies propulsion like fish has been based on the idea that the van Karman vortices are rearranged has dominated the field. This belief based on the idea that vortices thrust the fish forward. According to Google Scholar, there are around 20,000 papers that swear that this idea is the ultimate, absolute, and unadulterated true. According to this deep religious belief, the vortices are responsible for the fish thrust. These researchers have mountains of the “evidence” with a huge ocean of beautiful images to prove it. Liao et al (2003) went further and asserted that even energy can be extracted from the vortices. In fact, Liao et al provided a “proof” how the fish extracted energy from the vortices moving along a certain path as they stated:

“Body kinematics have a consistent relation with the frequency and phase of the vortex wake across several cylinder treatments (11), which supports our hypothesis that trout can extract energy from the wake in addition to benefiting from drafting in the reduced flow behind the cylinder.”

There are about 800 citations in support of violations of first and second law of thermodynamics for this paper^{1 2}. The fish body easily can detect the least resistance path nothing else in that case, there is no energy extraction. Beside this strange claim, there is no explanation how energy is extracted (is it potential energy?).

In the early 191x Alfred Wegener (1912) discovered the continental drift. The scientific establishment had ridiculed him. For sometime they just ignore his work and evidence and they had their evidences and so much of it. The same is happening with fish propulsion, violations of thermodynamics laws means nothing for them³. In fact, this belief has penetrated to other areas with individuals who had exposure to thermodynamics background. Yet, no alarm bells were ringed by anyone! Furthermore, these researchers get awards and grants from governments and others to carry this belief (see for example (Lauder 2015) and (Fish and Rohr 1999)). Furthermore, Fish et al (1999) asserted that vortices are so powerful that they provide enough power for the dolphins leap out the water. It would be wonderful see the control volume or scientific explanation that can demonstrate this leap indeed caused by the vortices⁴. Yet, there are beautiful im-

¹One can only wonder about these citations. Did they really read the paper?

²Epps et al published the paper (Epps, Valdivia y Alvarado, Youcef-Toumi, and Techet 2009). They asked if they are aware that their paper violates the first and second laws of thermo, they did not have an answer! And they are proud of these violations. Do they thinking that no one will find about it.

³Actually, they have been trying to ignore it and hope that it will go away. They have ignored all communications. Maybe they will respond to this paper. They are invited to explain how their work is not violating the second law in any form.

⁴One of the users suggested that these researchers possess the vortex bending power/ability (see the Avatar the Last Air Bender).

ages of a vortices in the locations where dolphins leap out of the water. The fact that there are vortices is no proof of the source(s) of the propulsion⁵. Vortices appear in cases of leftover energy that results from different velocities not additional energy.

In the first part of this series (Bar-Meir 2022b) demonstrated how the common approach violates the first and second laws of thermodynamics. The second paper in the series (Bar-Meir 2022c) provides an alternative explanation how the common belief violates the thermodynamics laws and most importantly two new models: one) to explain the physics of how tail curvatures makes propulsion efficient and two) examine the tail height variations effects on the propulsion.

2 Different Kinds of Pectoral Fins

The current discussion deals with the fish locomotion for which the pectoral fins are responsible for quarter (actually even less) or more of the energy supply/power and the fins are moving like oars (rotating front and back in marine terminology: yawing). The pectoral fins can have different “design” categories to create locomotion which first will be presented here. Every each of these fins design has, from engineering point of view, a vastly different mechanism. Yet, at the end of the day, all propelling fins have to create a jet in the opposite direction of the desired direction (except for the navigation purposes). Note, the vortices do not provide propulsion, only it is a mechanism in which energy is shed and in some ways to reduce the resistance (for other bodies). Fish propulsion is like having different pumps but with different techniques (positive displacement (piston, gear, screw, etc), centrifugal etc) but yet they have to move the substance (mostly liquid) to other side.

There are several “designs” that aquatic bodies used for their pectoral fins. These pectoral fins can be roughly categorized by their main usages. There are fishes like sharks that use the fins as stabilizers and navigation devices. Some fishes use the fins for locomotion which can be either moving up and down verse moving front and back. Some fins are used as the side oars of the boat and this movement sometimes is referred as BCF locomotion. Some of the fins are oscillating and some are undulating. The oscillating fins are basically rotating plates while the undulating fins are changing shape “plate” and they achieve a better and more power propulsion (or reduction of the resistance) as results. The movement of fish and other aquatic bodies can be characterized by using relatively simple fluid mechanics principles.

A short point has to be mentioned, the folding and bending are not the same and they are different. The bending refers

⁵Who are those who are citing these papers with all the violations of the thermo laws. Their keyboard should be confiscated immediately unless the citation to point to the errors.

FIGURE 1. Goliath Grouper folding the left pectoral fin. While Grouper has incredible ability to control fin, the fin can not be bent. The fish is caught and is upside down.

to have a hinge in the middle of the pectoral fin like birds while folding refers to strong undulation in which is almost like a folding. In plain English, if the line between the tail and head is the fish axis then bending axis is parallel to it and folding is perpendicular to it. The folding appears only in limited fishes such as Goliath Grouper which can fold the fin to half see port fin in fig. 1.

3 Pectoral Fins Classifications

The classification of the pectoral fins should be according to the relative length of the fin to the body (this ratio was chosen due to the poor man dimensional analysis not present here) and distribution as a distance from the pivot point. The fin prime number is defined (see fig. 2 for the definitions) as

$$F_d = \frac{\text{fin depth}}{\text{fish length}} \quad (1)$$

It turn out that this dimensionless number is less significance as compared to what appriori (initially) was considered by this author (R^4 and not R^5).

The second dimensional number is the ratio of the fin depth to the fish length.

$$F_l = \frac{\text{Fin Length}}{\text{Fish Length}} \quad (2)$$

The largest value observed for ratio is about $F_l = 0.8$ for fish like ray, sting, and flat shark etc. Some of fishes in this category use their pectoral fins as airplanes/birds and the main motion of the fins is up and down (rolling in marine terminology). This kind

FIGURE 2. Demonstration how the fish pectoral fin are measured. In this depiction the length and depth are portrayed.

of movement is especially correct for birds which dive into the water such as Atlantic puffin. While the puffins are not fish, yet they used their wing similarly to pectoral fins (for engineering point of view, this usage is what important for the analysis). As usual in nature, things get more complicate and some seals use their pectoral fins in angle which is both up and down and front and back. This analysis discuss this category but does not provide a model for it at this stage. While this number turned out to be more significant than F_d , a more important dimensionless number/function is

$$L(\xi) = \frac{L(x/L)}{\text{Fin Length}} \quad (3)$$

After the analysis and viewing some additional videos, it seems reasonable to consider the dimensionless area number as

$$A_b = \frac{A_{fin}}{A_{body\ side}} \quad (4)$$

This ratio demonstrates, for example, the difference between air propulsion which is around 1 vs. water propulsion is around 0.1 (if the ratio was only based the density, it should be in the range of 1:1000). The difference between fast aquatic bodies like seals and slow body like siamese fighting fish (*Betta splendens*) is indication of the relationship between the power/force and speed. This ratio of seals is bout twice as compared to siamese fighting fish. While not conclusive, there are some indications that this number might be important. For example, Trigger fish has very small ratio of about 4% which indicate that the fin is mostly used for navigation and hovering. For Clown fish the ratio is about 9% which is twice the Trigger fish and the main use of the fin is for slow locomotion, sometime even in the reverse direction. The giant Trevally has relative very large ratio of 13% which maybe used to gain extra power to leap out the water. The flying fish has the largest of all fishes which is more than one, if the pelvic fins also included. Yet, the flying fish does not used the fin in the

water as it might be too large (structurally not sound in water). The importance of the velocity ratio at this stage is not conclusive. While this pseudo dimensional analysis seems satisfactory for some, it is not a full scale dimensional analysis which missing in this area overall (no funding ?). The dimensional analysis is important scientific tool that can and should be used in many situations and conditions. It can be used even in philosophy like this case (Bar-Meir 2022d). It also used in related fields such as ship stability (Bar-Meir 2022e). It also used in totally different area like die casting (Bar-Meir 1995).

Babenko (2020) compiled a list of marine mammal which show that the F_d number which is in range of 0.2-0.3. This data set also states the velocity of creature. Examining the data does not provide any real information how this dimensionless number relevant to the speed. The real important information such as the height as the function of the distance from the hinge. No research was found about this issue. In the word “research” here, it means that neither one) underlying structure to sustain this force or two) relationship between the sizes of the pectoral fin and the speeds (maybe Reynolds number) does not exist. Yet, this poor man analysis provides only a taste of the effects of various parameters.

In the previous paper (Bar-Meir 2022c) in the series, it was shown that a **simple** pushing forward and pushing back actually results in zero net force/momentum. Saffman (1967) suggested intuitively that fin is modified in the power portion as compared to the “recoil” (back) portion of the stroke. The power portion is when fin push backward and the “recoil” is forward. According to Saffman, the difference in the shape is the responsible factor for difference in the force/power and hence allow for the propulsion. Interesting that while examining the fish stability Weihs (2002) suggested that the same idea is responsible for source of the locomotion. It seems that this idea is the most intuitive yet unfortunately it is not the main cause for most fishes as it will be shown below.

In man made oar, the oar (fin) is taken out of the water to achieve the propulsion (reduce the force back in the return stroke). Yet, there is no specific measurement/model that describe how this achieved and what actually happening for submersed oar. It simply based on the intuition which will be examined here. This idea looks reasonable but the question remains, how this difference is obtained. There are several possibilities and two most reasonable: one) the inclination changes the direction of the area⁶, two) the actual undulation which reduces the “effective” area. The first change partially directed force away from the motion direction (it is trigonometrically related). These two options seem to have effect in the range of 10% to 50% for most fishes (the Goliath Grouper has probably the largest change of area effect observed by this author. In fact, the effect is large enough to change nature of the mechanism to pitch propulsion.).

⁶Area has a direction, as opposed to common belief, is perpendicular to surface.

Since every thing help, these factors are important, yet different mechanism/reason for the propulsion which will be presented down below.

In the literature there are only verbiage without any specific model beside the van Karman vortices which now it is clear that it should be erased from the realm of considered possibilities. This author was challenged by a user to provide a model for the movement of the pectoral fins that acts as oar⁷. Hence, this issue become academic exploration.

The pectoral fins are like large hands that a swimmer would used in a breast stroke swimming style. In fact, another user suggested that fish is doing just that. While birds have a hinge, the fish does not have a hinge in the middle of the fin to bend it. In the examination, it seem that some fish indeed using this strategy by turning the fin and make the effective cross section smaller. Some of the Goliath Grouper and a like are moving some time in a new category of pitch propulsion (rotating not up and down or front and back) which is out of scope of this paper.

4 Calculating the Thrust

FIGURE 3. Schematic of fish pectoral fin shown in the top and side views. The purple color showing the typical extent of the fin. The pitch rotation is to reduce drag during return part of the stroke. The angle γ_2 is the “working” range for the fin strong. Notice that $d\gamma/dt = \omega$ for any gamma.

For the sake of isolating the various effects, the fin is assumed with a uniform height and the fish can rotate the fin in a pitch direction as modification (see fig. 3 for the explanation). The main movement is the yaw when the power portion is counter-clockwise while (obviously) return is clockwise. Some concepts are taken from (Bar-Meir 2022c) but are repeated for consistency and completeness. A liquid in a still condition and is approached

⁷This series increases every time a new paper is published, there is more demand.

by a moving solid wall is replaced by a fixed wall with a moving liquid toward it. This change of coordinate system makes it easier for people conceptualize the Bernoulli's equation. The change in the pressure difference (not the pressure) is a function of the velocity toward the wall. According to Bernoulli's equation (neglecting the gravity) the change of the pressure is $\Delta P \sim \rho U^2/2$.

FIGURE 4. Schematic of fish pectoral fin zones for propulsion due to the fin.

5 The Angle Zone

The control volume is around the fin and hence the thin layer of liquid attached to fin is stationary. The external force is at the connection between the fin and body. The energy/momentum losses are neglected (a coefficient for loss can be applied to improve calculations.). The work per element of the fin is

$$dW_p = \frac{\rho}{2} \int_{\gamma_3}^{\gamma_3+\gamma_2} \left(\frac{U}{\omega r} \right)^2 \sin \theta \overbrace{h r d\theta}^{dA} \quad (5)$$

θ is defined in the fig. 3 (the origin is at the armpit for θ and r) and fig. 4 and r is the local radius of the (part) fin. The differential path the force is moving on is $r d\theta$. The differential area is $h dr$ and $\sin \theta$ is use to take only component that pushing the fish. The actual work on the element of the fin is

$$dW_a = \frac{\rho h}{2} \int_{\gamma_3}^{\gamma_3+\gamma_2} (\omega r)^2 r d\theta \quad (6)$$

In real life ω is not constant and the initial part and final part require modifications. However, if these parts are ignored, the angular velocity can be approximated as a constant. Notice, the other side of the fin was considered for similar arguments in (Bar-Meir 2022c) and is not included. Basically statement means that force is about this range, $(\rho U^2/2)$. And, the experimental

work has to determine the correction coefficient. After the integration the element work in the thin arc eq. (5) is

$$dW_p = \frac{\rho \omega^2 h r^3}{2} (\cos(\gamma_3 + \gamma_2) - \cos \gamma_3) \quad (7)$$

The work, in angle zone, is obtained by integration of all the thin arcs as a function of r from 0 to R to be

$$W_p = \int_0^R dW_p dr = \frac{\rho \omega^2 h R^4}{8} (\cos(\gamma_3 + \gamma_2) - \cos \gamma_3) \quad (8)$$

The actual work is

$$W_a = \int_0^R dW_a dr = \frac{\rho \omega^2 h R^3}{8} (\gamma_2) \quad (9)$$

The efficiency or the ratio of propulsion work vs the actual work is

$$\eta = \frac{\cos(\gamma_3 + \gamma_2) - \cos \gamma_3}{\gamma_2} \quad (10)$$

The ratio relates the amount of energy obtained in the propulsion with the energy that is invested into the fin. Also these angles are not "strong/fix" values rather estimate of angles. Yet, it provides a reasonable clues to the efficiency. Notice as the fin get longer the amount of work or power obtained is a strong function of fin length, R , as it is R^4 . This fact can be observed by examining the video (at rumble and youtube) showing the "jet" action for giant Trevally leaping out water to catch bird and seal catching sardines. Yet, the efficiency does not change. It seems that this zone is not used for cruising swimming⁸.

6 The "Jet" Zone

FIGURE 5. Control volume of the fish pectoral fin in the jet zone confined by the fin and fish body.

⁸Where are the real biologists when you need them?

In the jet zone two equations are required have be solved. The equations for mass and momentum balance in the control volume are suggested in (2022a). The mass conservation of the control volume shown in fig. 5 reads

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{c.v.} \rho_s dV = - \int_{S_{cv}} \rho U_{rn} dA \quad (11)$$

This control volume has only one exit, the volume varies with time, and the change is due to the pectoral fin movement. The velocity at the exit is not uniform and has a small component in y direction. For simplicity, it is assumed that the velocity is uniform and it is left to others improve this part of the analysis. Hence, eq. (11) is reduced to

$$\frac{\rho \omega R^2}{2} = UR\rho(\gamma_1 - \omega t) \longrightarrow U = \frac{\omega R}{2(\gamma_1 - \omega t)} \quad (12)$$

where t is time and is measured from the time the fin from location at γ_1 to t^* . U is the exit (averaged) velocity from control volume. The t^* is the time that it takes the fin to reach almost to the body from γ_1 . The height h is canceled out in the analysis. According to eq. (12), the jet velocity increases as the fin approaches to body. Normally when the velocity approaches to infinity, something breaks in the model either ω decreases or something else happens. Additional point, the velocity as a function of r or x can be obtained from a similar concept as the smaller control volume. Hence, it can be written that

$$U(r) = \frac{\omega r}{2(\gamma_1 - \omega t)} \quad (13)$$

and for small angles, the velocity can be considered as $U(x)$. The velocity close to ‘‘armpit’’ is zero and increases linearly with distance from it. The general momentum equation (Bar-Meir 2022a) is

$$\sum F_x + \int_{c.v.} (\mathbf{g} \cdot \hat{i}) \rho dV - \int_{c.v.} \mathbf{P} \cos \theta_x dA + \int_{c.v.} \tau_x \cdot d\mathbf{A} = \frac{t}{dt} \int_{c.v.} \rho \mathbf{U}_x dV + \int_{c.v.} \rho \mathbf{U}_x \cdot \mathbf{U}_{rn} dA \quad (14)$$

which reduced in this case to

$$F_x = \frac{t}{dt} \int_{c.v.} \rho \mathbf{U}_x dV + \int_{c.v.} \rho \mathbf{U}_x \cdot \mathbf{U}_{rn} dA \quad (15)$$

Several terms in eq. (14) were eliminated based on the following

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assumptions: the gravity does not play important role (larger error for a larger fish) the pressure at the exit of the pectoral fin is as the surroundings. This assumption can be improved but here it is a quick fix for the purpose of the discussion. The term with the shear stress is assumed to be vanishing based on the assumption of the flow direction. The momentum inside the control volume using eq. (13) results in

$$\mathcal{M} = \rho \int_0^R \int_{\pi-\gamma_1}^{\pi} \frac{\omega r \cos \theta}{2(\gamma_1 - \omega t)} r d\theta dr \quad (16)$$

which results in the momentum in the control volume as

$$\mathcal{M} = -\frac{\rho \omega R^3 \sin \gamma_1}{6(\gamma_1 - \omega t)} \quad (17)$$

The derivative of eq. (17) with respect to time is

$$\frac{d.\mathcal{M}}{dt} = \frac{\rho \omega^2 R^3 \sin \gamma_1}{6(\gamma_1 - \omega t)} \quad (18)$$

Hence, the force that acting on the body is

$$F_x = \frac{5\rho \omega^2 R^3 \sin \gamma_1}{12(\gamma_1 - \omega t)} \quad (19)$$

Shown in the figure with initial boundary of γ_1 and final at $\gamma_1 + \gamma_2$. Notice that angles are not precisely measured since soft tissues are measured. Nevertheless reasonable estimate can be obtained. Notice asymmetry of the angles $\gamma_3 \gg \gamma_1$. The reason for the asymmetry is that fin is for small γ_3 , does not produce any propulsion (forward) as oppose to γ_1 . For γ_3 the liquid is pushed away from the fish and actually changes the gravity centroid off course. For small γ_1 the liquid is squeezed between the body and fin and pushed backward which is desirable. Figure 4 exhibits the different zones for which fin’s force depends on the angle. In the ‘‘useless’’ zone is the zone the fin mostly pushes the gravity centroid out desired motion or provides reverse velocity. The further the γ_3 increase the fin is more effective. But, there is new mechanism which kick in and actually the power increases. In the ‘‘mix’’ zone, the component in the direction of the movement is reduced while the perpendicular part is pushed by the body in total propulsion increases. The zone is the ‘‘jet’’ in which almost all the liquid is jetting out as fin and body squeezing it out.

In this discussion, the force in angle zone is calculated because it largest zone (subjectively missing some input from biol-

ogists) and because it is easy⁹ to calculate and demonstrate the main effect.

7 The Big Picture

In the discussion of these zones so far the details become source of interest while the big picture was not in the focus. What these results mean to pectoral fin propulsion? The main attempt was to explain how pectoral fin work. Weihs and Saffman advocated the idea of change cross area (revolve in pitch) and undulation. The rotation has two effects one of which is undesirable. The undesirable effect is that the force pushes the aquatic creature from the path. These models shows that the propulsion depends on the angular velocity of rotation at least as ω^2 . Thus, for example, if pushing the power portion of the stroke is twice as fast the return (recoil) portion then the net power efficiency is about $(1 - 0.5^2) = 0.75$ or in other words the fish has get 75% while the previous suggestion it on fraction of this amount. Thus, including all these suggestions (change of cross area, undulation, and change velocity) means that the creature can achieve almost 90% efficiency (lost of 10% in return stroke). Additionally, if the fin is operating in a different zone it can achieve different effects. For example, operating in the “useless” zone fin can push the fish backward. With or without the combination of the tail it can create hovering situation.

In Roh and Gharib (2019) examined honey bees by placing them in water surface. While the researchers were under the influence of the dominate theory, they actually found, not intentionally, evidence that the time for power stroke and return stroke are different about ratio of 2 (check fig 2 and 3 in their paper which is with a “restrictive license”). The current models presented here also explained the hovering and other maneuvering ability. This paper solely deals with locomotion and not stability. Thus, there is no discussion on stability within these models.

8 Results and Discussion

What has been achieved in this paper? It was discovered that pectoral fin can be diversified propulsion device. It can propel the fish back or front. In fact, it was discovered that fin has different zones of operation in which the fin has different effects. The last fact was not discussed in the scientific literature before. For the first time analytical relationship between the fin movement and force is described. Furthermore, it was shown how the efficiency related the fin movement. Simple model can explain the propulsion for different zones. Even the “useless” zone actually provides backward propulsion. Thus, the gap in our understanding how fish or mammal achieves this desired thrust direction has become significantly narrower. It was shown how the aquatic

creature can obtain extra push to leap of the water or gain in hunting maneuverability. The fin has several angle ranges that they are more efficient. Comparison of this list achievements to dominated model understanding which violates the first and second law of thermodynamics, immediately shows the progress in the understanding fish locomotion. While the instincts are not the best tool to judge, in this case it is correct. The reader probably observed that the most intensive part of swimming when the hands (in breast stroke) are moving closer to the body gaining speed but are harder to perform.

Concluding Remarks

Obviously this papers series is different from all the papers published in this area because not only the papers proposed totally new idea(s) but “alleged” that old model, at least in part, violates the first and second law of thermodynamics. The author is not a shame to exposed that the establishment belief is full with conceptional errors (and they can go after him or ignore him as much they like). Thus, if you believe that the ideas and analysis in this paper are correct, you should change the way you deal with the fish/aquatic propulsion. If you do not believe in these ideas, you are welcome to criticize the this author’s current or future papers (all or any of papers in this area), in any form, all remarks in writing or electronic are appreciated (please do not call this author who do not like to deal with too emotional people.). There are several web cites and forums dedicated to criticize and discuss this author’s work for you to choose from. This paper is the third part of the installment in this series. Currently, the fourth and fifth parts are in a draft form and may or may not be published and might join the faith of many unpublished papers of this author, laying in his boxes. A small point, in writing these papers a new technology was used. The equations derivations were typed straight into enclosed confidential and supper confidential environments (for this author eyes only) which do not appear in the final version. Hence, if something is rasping, it is due to this dual writing.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many cite his work or jobs he held but only point to how many breakthroughs he made. In die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are main pliers.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spend millions promoting these beliefs. Since the problems were not solved, hundreds of CFD teams from over the world attempted to solve it in vain where this author solve it. The establishment fight against publishing

⁹Actually the jet zone is the easiest to calculate.

these discoveries.

Furthermore, the author solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation) and which people like Sandip Ghosal plagiarize. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass. The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this authors. When you search on Google and type “basics of fluid” it offers Genick Bar–Meir as first or second results. This fact is a positive proof that the establishment efforts to silence this author has had failed.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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